

Consumer Attitude Toward New Products in Dhaka City: A Case Study of Two Products

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Abstract: Attitudes are evaluative statements — either favorable or unfavorable — concerning objects, people or events. Attitude, which consists of cognitive, affective and behavioral components, reflects how one feels about something. New product includes new-to-the-world products, exiting products that are targeted to new markets or market segments, improvements and revisions of existing products, and so on. The article depicts an empirical study in which 200 consumers who lived in Dhaka City were asked about their attitudes toward vacuum cleaners and rice cookers, which have been selected as new products for this study. Vacuum cleaners and rice cookers are new products in the sense that they are existing products targeted at new market (Bangladesh). The principal findings of this study are that consumers of Dhaka City have a weakly positive attitude toward vacuum cleaners and rice cookers. In addition, age, gender, education, marital status, and family income influence the nature of consumers' attitudes toward vacuum cleaners and rice cookers as new products. But occupation does not always influence consumer attitude toward rice cookers as a new product.

1. Introduction

An attitude is an enduring organization of motivational, emotional, perceptual, and cognitive processes with respect to some aspect of our environment. It is a learned predisposition to respond in a consistently favorable or unfavorable manner with respect to a given object. Thus, an attitude is the way we think, feel, and act toward some aspect of our environment such as a retail store, television program, or product (Hawkins, Mothersbaugh, and Best, 2007, p. 396). Attitudes are an outcome of psychological processes. As a result, they cannot be directly observable or measured but can be inferred from what people say or what they do.

The purpose of the present paper is to examine the nature of attitudes of consumers toward two new products in Dhaka City—vacuum cleaner and rice cooker. Since there are many new products in the market at any given time, it is difficult to observe consumer attitudes toward all new products in one survey. Attitudes of a particular consumer toward new products vary from product to product. As a result, it is convenient to observe attitudes of consumers toward one or two new products at a time. Based on the

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observations of the nature of consumer attitudes toward one or two new products, generalization, to a great extent, can be done quite plausibly for a group of consumers with a particular culture and heritage.

Before analyzing the nature of consumer attitudes toward the two new products, it will be useful to have a clear idea about the terms “attitude” and “new product.”

Attitudes have three components: cognitive (beliefs) component, affective (feelings) component, and behavioral or conative (response tendencies) component ((Hawkins, Mothersbaugh, and Best, 2007, pp. 397-403; Shhiffman and Kanuk, 2004, pp. 256-259).

Cognitive Component: The cognitive component consists of a consumer’s beliefs about an object. For most attitude objects, we have a number of beliefs. For example, we may believe that Sprite (i) is popular with younger consumers, (ii) contains a lot of caffeine, (iii) is competitively priced, and (iv) is made by a large company. The total configuration of beliefs about this brand of soda represents the cognitive component of an attitude toward Sprite. It is important to keep in mind that beliefs need not be correct or true; they only need to exist.

“Many beliefs about attributes are evaluative in nature. That is, high gas mileage, attractive styling, and reliable performance are generally viewed as positive beliefs. The more positive beliefs that are associated with a brand, the more positive each belief is; and the easier it is for the individual to retrieve or recall the beliefs, the more favorable the overall cognitive component is presumed to be. And, since all of the components of an attitude are generally consistent, the more favorable the overall attitude is. This logic underlies what is known as **the multiattribute attitude model**” (Hawkins, Mothersbaugh, and Best, 2007, p. 397).

Affective Component: Our feelings or emotional reactions to an object represent the affective component of an attitude. A consumer who states, “I like Sprite,” or “Sprite is a terrible soda,” is expressing the results of an emotional or affective evaluation of the product. This overall evaluation may be simply a vague, general feeling developed without cognitive information or beliefs about the product. Or, it may be the result of several evaluations of the product’s performance on each of several attributes. Thus, the statements, “Sprite tastes bad,” and “Sprite is not good for your health,” imply a negative affective reaction to specific aspects of the product that, in combination with feelings about attributes, will determine the overall reaction to the brand (Hawkins, Best, and Coney, 2001, pp. 398-399).

Since products, like other objects we react to, are evaluated in the context of a specific situation, a consumer’s affective reaction to a product may change as the situation changes. For example, a consumer may believe that (i) Sprite has caffeine and (ii) caffeine will keep you awake. These beliefs may cause a positive affective response when

a consumer needs to stay awake to study for an examination and a negative response when s/he wants to drink something late in the evening that won't keep her/him awake later (Hawkins, Best, and Coney, 2001, p. 398).

“Due to unique motivations and personalities, past experiences, reference groups, and physical conditions, individuals may evaluate the same belief differently. Some individuals may have a positive feeling toward the belief that “Sprite is made by a large multinational company” while others could respond with a negative reaction...” (Hawkins, Best, and Coney, 2001, p. 398).

“Despite individual variations, most individuals within a given culture react in a similar manner to beliefs that are closely associated with cultural values... (T)here often is a strong association between how a belief is evaluated and a related value that is of importance within a culture” (Hawkins, Best, and Coney, 2001, pp. 398-399).

While feelings are often the result of evaluating specific attributes of a product, they can precede and influence cognitions. In fact, one may come to like a product without acquiring any cognitive beliefs about that product. Indeed, our initial reaction to a product may be one of like or dislike without any cognitive basis for the feeling. This initial affect can then influence how we react to the product itself.

Behavioral Component: The behavioral component of an attitude is one's tendency to respond in a certain manner toward an object or activity. A series of decision to purchase or not purchase Diet Coke or to recommend it or other brands to friends would reflect the behavioral component of an attitude. The behavioral component provides response tendencies or behavioral intentions. Our actual behaviors reflect these intentions as they are modified by the situation in which the behavior will occur.

“Since behavior generally directed toward an entire object, it is less likely to be attribute specific than are either beliefs or affect. However, this is not always the case, particularly with respect to retail outlets. For example, in U.S.A. many consumers buy canned goods at discount or warehouse-type grocery outlets but purchase meats and fresh vegetables at regular supermarkets. Thus, for retail outlets, it is possible and common to react behaviorally to specific beliefs about the outlet. This is generally difficult to do with products because we have to either buy or not buy the complete product” (Hawkins, Best, and Coney, 2001, pp. 398-399).

Attitudes serve four key functions for individuals. These functions are briefly described below (Hawkins, Mothersbaugh, and Best, 2007, p. 396):

Knowledge Function: Some attitudes serve primarily as a means of organizing beliefs about objects or activities such as brands and shopping. These attitudes may be accurate or inaccurate with respect to “objective” reality, but the attitude will often determine subsequent behaviors rather than “reality.” For example, a consumer's attitude toward

cola drinks may be “they all taste the same.” This consumer would be likely to purchase the least expensive or most convenient brand. This would be true even if, in a taste test, the consumer could tell the brands apart and would prefer one over the others. Firms like Pepsi spend considerable effort to influence consumers’ beliefs about colas.

Value-expressive Function: Other attitudes are formed and serve to express an individual’s central values and self-concept. Thus, consumers who value nature and the environment are likely to develop attitudes about products and activities that are consistent with that value. These consumers are likely to express support for environment protection initiatives, to recycle, and to purchase and use “green” products.

Utilitarian Function: This function is based on operant conditioning. We tend to form favorable attitudes toward objects and activities that are rewarding and negative attitudes toward those that are not. Marketers frequently promise rewards in advertising and conduct extensive product testing to be sure the products are indeed rewarding.

Ego-defensive Function: Attitudes are often formed and used to defend our egos and images against threats and shortcomings. Products promoted as very macho may be viewed favorably by men who are insecure in their masculinity. Or, individuals who feel threatened in social situations may form favorable attitudes toward products and brands that promise success or at least safety in such situation. These individuals would be likely to have favorable attitudes toward popular brands and styles of cloths and to use personal care products such as deodorants, dandruff shampoo, and mouthwash.

Any given attitude can perform multiple functions, though one may predominate. Marketers need to be aware of the function that attitudes relevant to the purchase and use of their brands fulfill or could fulfill for their target markets.

Attitudes are formed as the result of many influences. They represent an important influence on an individual’s lifestyle. In this paper, we will describe attitudes of different consumers toward two new products.

Categories of New Products

Booz, Allen, and Hamilton (1982) identified six categories of new products:

1. New-to-the-world products: New products that create an entirely new market.
2. New product lines: New products that allow a company to enter an established market for the first time.
3. Additions to existing product lines: New products that supplement a company’s established product lines (package sizes, flavors, and so on).
4. Improvements and revisions of existing products: New products that provide improved performance or greater perceived value and replace existing products.

5. Repositioning: Existing products that are targeted to new markets or market segments.
6. Cost reductions: New products that provide similar performance at lower cost.

It is important to note that there are controversies among the academics in considering the 6th category mentioned above as new products.

Greet Hofstede (2001) identified four dimensions or characteristics of cultures of different countries. “The four dimensions are as follows: the Individual/Collective Index (IDV), which focuses on self-orientation; the Power Distance Index (PDI), which focuses on authority orientation; the Uncertainty Avoidance Index (UAI), which focuses on risk orientation; and the Masculinity/Femininity Index (MAS), which focuses on assertiveness and achievement” (Cateora and Graham, 2007, p. 106). In a subsequent study, a fifth dimension, Long-Term Orientation (LTO) was identified as focusing on temporal orientation (Hofstede and Bond, 1998). Bangladesh is low in IDV and thus it is expected that consumers in Bangladesh have positive attitude toward a new product if it can be used collectively by family members. On the other hand, Bangladesh is high in UAI and thus it is expected that consumers of Bangladesh have a negative attitude toward new products (for detailed discussions on the five dimensions of cultures and their implications in studying consumer behavior please see Cateora and Graham, (2007), p. 106-107). Therefore, attitudes of consumers of Dhaka City toward rice cooker and vacuum cleaner are subject to empirical study; no *a priori* conclusion can be made about their attitudes towards these two new products. Because vacuum cleaner and rice cooker, on one hand, are used for the family or household purposes, and not for the purposes of an individual consumer. Therefore, consumers should have a positive attitude toward these new products. On the other hand, these two products are new products in Dhaka City and thus consumers will tend to avoid risk of buying new products, that is, consumers of Dhaka City should have a negative attitude toward these two new products.

2. Objective

The objective of the present study is to analyze the nature of attitudes of consumers of Dhaka City toward two new products—household vacuum cleaner and household rice cooker.

3. Methodology and Data Source

As mentioned earlier, the purpose of the present study is to analyze the nature of attitudes of consumers of Dhaka City toward two new products—household vacuum cleaner and household rice cooker. Since there are many new products in the market at any given time, it is not possible to observe consumer attitudes toward all new products in one survey. Attitudes of a particular consumer toward new products vary from product to

product and attitudes of different consumers toward a particular product vary from consumer to consumer. For this study, two products were selected to observe attitudes of consumers toward new products.

For the present study, household vacuum cleaner and rice cooker for household use were selected. 200 samples irrespective of gender, academic background, occupation, marital status, and religion were selected on the basis of convenient sampling procedure from a number of localities of Dhaka City. The localities provided a sample of adult consumers with geographic and demographic dispersions. Among the samples 92 are males and 108 are females who are over 25 years of age and 143 of them are married. Monthly family income of the respondents is Taka 40,000 or above.

Respondents were asked how household vacuum cleaner and rice cooker are important for their household using a three-point scale: (i) not a useful product, (ii) a somewhat useful product, and (iii) a very useful product. Cross tabulations are performed to measure the relationship between demographic and economic characteristics and their attitudes toward these new products.

4. Findings of the Study

The respondents were asked to express their attitudes toward household vacuum cleaner and rice cooker as new products with three statements: “a very useful product,” “a somewhat useful product,” and “not a useful product”. Their answers are summarized in the following tables.

Table 1: Consumer Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner by Age

		Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Age	25 - 45	20 (14%)	57 (40%)	64 (46%)	141
	Above45	12 (20%)	26 (44%)	21 (36%)	59
Total		32 (16%)	83 (42%)	85 (42%)	200

Table 2: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.057	2	.358
Likelihood Ratio	2.045	2	.360
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.046	1	.153
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 1 shows 141 of the respondents belong to the age group of 25 to 45 and rest 59 respondents are over 45 years. Out of 200 respondents, 32 (16%) said that household vacuum cleaner is not a useful product, and 83 (42%) said that it is somewhat useful. The rest 85 (42%) said that it is a very useful product. Thus, irrespective of age, gender, educational background, marital status, and monthly income level, we find that consumer attitude toward household vacuum cleaner is on average weakly positive. On the other hand, out of 141 respondents of age between 25 and 45 years, 20 (14%) mentioned that vacuum cleaner is not a useful product whereas 64 (46%) of them rated that vacuum cleaner is a very useful product. The rest 57 (40%) are neutral. The Table also shows that 12 (20%) of the respondents of age above 45 years reported that vacuum cleaner is not a useful product. On the other hand, 21 (36%) of them mentioned that vacuum cleaner is a very useful product. The rest 26 (44%) mentioned that it is a somewhat useful product. Here the sample is divided between younger and older consumers and cross tabulation of these two demographic groups show that age is unrelated with the nature of attitude toward vacuum cleaner (see Table 2).

Table 3: Attitude Toward Rice Cooker by Age

		Attitude Toward Rice Cooker			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Age	25-45	28 (20%)	65 (46%)	48 (34%)	141 (71%)
	Above45	21 (36%)	27 (45%)	11 (19%)	59 (39%)
Total		49 (24%)	92 (46%)	59 (30%)	200

Table 4: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.548	2	.023
Likelihood Ratio	7.578	2	.023
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.464	1	.006
N of Valid Cases	200		

From the Table 3, it is observed that out of 141 younger respondents 28 (20%) reported that rice cooker is not a useful product, whereas 48 (34%) of them mentioned that it is a very useful product. The rest 65 (46%) are neutral. It is also found that out of 59 older respondents (aged above 45 years) 21 (36%) rated that rice cooker is not a useful product. On the other hand, 11 (19%) of them mentioned that it is a very useful product. The rest

27 (45%) are neutral. In addition, out of total 200 respondents of the both age groups 59 (30%) mentioned that it is a very useful product and 49 (24%) stated that it is not a useful product. Thus, we see that consumer attitude toward rice cooker (irrespective of age, gender, educational level, marital status, and monthly family income of consumers) are weakly positive, and younger consumers have more favorable attitude toward rice cooker than older consumers. In addition, cross tabulation of these two demographic groups shows that age is related with attitude toward rice cooker (see Table 4)

Table 5: Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner by Gender

		Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Gender	Male	20 (22%)	51 (55%)	21 (23%)	92 (46%)
	Female	15 (14%)	29 (27%)	64 (59%)	108 (54%)
Total		35 (18%)	80 (40%)	85 (42%)	200

Table 6: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	27.413	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	28.355	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.035	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 5 shows that out of 200 respondents, 92 (46%) are male and the rest 108 (54%) are female. Out of these 92 male respondents, 22 (22%) reported that vacuum cleaner is not a useful product while 21 (23%) of them mentioned that it is very useful. The rest 51 (55%) showed neutral attitude toward vacuum cleaner. Thus, it can be concluded that attitudes of male consumers toward vacuum cleaner are mixed. On the other hand, out of 108 female respondents 64 (59%) said that vacuum cleaner is a very useful product, and only 15 (14%) said that it is not a useful product. The rest 29 showed neutral attitude. Thus, it can be concluded that attitudes of female consumers toward vacuum cleaner are quite positive. In aggregate, out of 200 respondents, 85 (42%) has positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner whereas only 35 (18%) have negative attitudes toward vacuum cleaner. Therefore, it can be plausibly concluded that irrespective of age, gender, educational background, and marital status of consumers, their attitudes, on average, toward vacuum

cleaner in Dhaka City is positive. However, consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner in Dhaka City significantly varies across gender (see Table 6).

Table 7: Attitude Toward Rice Cooker by Gender

		Attitude Toward Rice Cooker			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Gender	Male	32 (35%)	54 (58%)	6 (7%)	92 (46%)
	Female	17 (16%)	38 (35%)	53 (49%)	108 (54%)
Total		49 (25%)	92 (46%)	59 (25%)	200

Table 8: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	43.816	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	49.176	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	34.890	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

From Table 7 it is seen that out of 92 male respondents, only 6 (7%) stated that rice cooker is a very useful product. On the other hand, 32 (35%) male respondents have negative attitude toward rice cooker. But the rest 54 (58%) have neutral attitude. These findings imply that male consumers in Dhaka City have weakly negative attitude towards rice cooker. On the other hand, out of 108 female respondents, 53 (49%) have positive attitude toward rice cooker and only 17 (16%) have negative attitude. The rest 38 (35%) have neutral attitude. In addition, out of all respondents, 85 (42%) have positive attitude and 35 (18%) have negative attitude. The rest 80 (40%) have neutral attitude. Thus, it can be concluded that in Dhaka City, consumer attitude toward rice cooker is slightly positive and female consumers' attitude toward rice cooker is more or less positive. Thus, it is found that in Dhaka City consumer attitude toward rice cooker varies across gender (see Table 8).

Table 9: Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner by Education

		Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Educa tion	Secondary	5 (45%)	4 (36%)	2 (18%)	11 (6%)
	Higher Secondary	14 (52%)	8 (30%)	5 (19%)	27 (14%)
	Graduate	7 (7%)	54 (53%)	40 (40%)	101 (50%)
	Post Graduate and higher	6 (10%)	17 (28%)	38 (62%)	61 (30%)
Total		32 (16%)	83 (41%)	85 (43%)	200

Table 10: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	52.506	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	44.898	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	28.272	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 9 shows that out of total 200 respondents, 11 (6%) have secondary, 27 (14%) have higher secondary, 101 (50%) have graduate, and the rest 61 (30%) have post graduate or higher education. Respondents with academic background between secondary and higher secondary levels are 38 in number (19%) and the rest 162 (81%) have graduate or higher education. Among the first group only 7 (out of 38, that is, 18%) have positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner, and 19 (50%) have negative attitude. The rest 12 (32%) are neutral. Thus, it can be concluded that consumers with lower educational background in Dhaka City have somewhat negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. Out of 162 respondents of second group 78 (48%) have positive attitude and only 13 (8%) have negative attitude. The rest 71 (44%) are neutral. Thus, it is found that consumers with higher education have somewhat positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner. On aggregate, 85 (43%) have positive attitude and 32 (16%) have negative attitude. The rest 83 (41%) are neutral. Thus, it can be concluded that in Dhaka City, consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner is slightly positive. On the other hand, consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner in Dhaka City varies across consumers based on their educational background (see Table 10).

Table 11 describes consumer attitude toward rice cooker according to educational background of the consumers in Dhaka City.

Table 11: Attitude Toward Rice Cooker by Education

		Attitude Toward Rice Cooker			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Educa tion	Secondary	6 (55%)	3 (27%)	2 (18%)	11 (6%)
	Higher Secondary	14 (52%)	7 (26%)	6 (22%)	27 (14%)
	Graduate	17 (17%)	68 (67%)	16 (16%)	101 (50%)
	Post Graduate and higher	12 (20%)	14 (23%)	35 (57%)	61 (30%)
Total		49 (25%)	92 (46%)	59 (29%)	200

Table 12: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	58.957	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	55.074	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	20.793	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Out of total 200 respondents, 11 (6%) have secondary, 27 (14%) have higher secondary, 101 (50%) have graduate, and the rest 61 (30%) have post graduate or higher education. Respondents with academic background between secondary and higher secondary levels are 38 in number (19%) and the rest 162 (81%) have graduate or higher education. Among the first group only 8 (out of 38, that is, 21%) have positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner, and 20 (53%) have negative attitude. The rest 10 (26%) are neutral. Thus, it can be concluded that consumers with lower educational background in Dhaka City have somewhat negative attitude toward rice cooker. Out of 162 respondents of second group 51 (31%) have positive attitude and 29 (18%) have negative attitude. The rest 82 (51%) are neutral. Thus, it is found that consumers with higher education have somewhat positive attitude toward rice cooker. On aggregate, 59 (29%) have positive attitude and 49 (25%) have negative attitude. The rest 92 (46%) are neutral. Thus, it can be concluded that in Dhaka City, consumer attitude toward rice cooker is slightly positive. On the other hand, consumer attitude toward rice cooker in Dhaka City varies across consumers based on their educational background (see Table 12).

Table 13 illustrates consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner by marital status. It can be found from the Table that out of total 200 respondents, 57 (29%) are single and the rest 143 (69%) are married. By “single respondents” we mean respondents who are not currently married. It can be found from the Table that out of 57 single respondents only 30 (53%) have positive attitude and 15 (26%) have negative attitude. The rest 12 (21%) are neutral. Thus we find that single consumers’ attitude toward vacuum cleaner is weakly positive. On the other hand, out of 143 married respondents, 55 (36%) have positive attitude, 71 (50%) have neutral attitude, and the rest 17 (12%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. Thus, it can be concluded that attitude of married consumers toward vacuum cleaner is more or less positive. In aggregate, 85 (42%) have positive, 83 (42%) have neutral, and the rest 32 (16%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. Thus, it can be safely concluded that consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner in Dhaka City is more or less positive. However, consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner varies depending on marital status of consumers (see Table 14).

Table 13: Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner by Marital Status

		Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Marital status	Single	15 (26%)	12 (21%)	30 (53%)	57(29%)
	Married	17 (12%)	71 (50%)	55 (36%)	143(69%)
Total		32(16%)	83(42%)	85(42%)	200

Table 14: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.259	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	15.848	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001	1	.982
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 15: Attitude Toward Rice Cooker by Marital Status

		Attitude Toward Rice Cooker			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Marital status	Single	20 (35%)	22 (39%)	15 (26%)	57 (29%)
	Married	29 (20%)	70 (49%)	44 (31%)	143 (69%)
Total		49(25%)	92 (46%)	59 (29%)	200

Table 16: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.872	2	.088
Likelihood Ratio	4.666	2	.097
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.799	1	.094
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 15 reports consumer attitude toward rice cooker by marital status. It can be found from the Table that out of 57 single respondents only 15 (26%) have positive attitude and 20 (35%) have negative attitude. The rest 22 (39%) are neutral. Thus we find that single consumers' attitude toward rice cooker is weakly negative. On the other hand, out of 143 married respondents, 44 (31%) have positive attitude, 70 (49%) have neutral attitude, and the rest 29 (20%) have negative attitude toward rice cooker. Thus, it can be concluded that attitude of married consumers toward rice cooker is weakly positive. In aggregate, 59 (29%) have positive, 92 (46%) have neutral, and the rest 49 (25%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. Thus, it can be concluded that consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner in Dhaka City is weakly positive. However, consumer attitude toward rice cooker varies depending on marital status of consumers (see Table 16).

Table 17 represents consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner by occupation. Out of total 200 respondents, 108 (54%) are executives and other professionals, 48 (24%) are businessmen, and the rest 44 (22%) are housewives.

Table 17: Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner by Occupation

		Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Occupation	Executives	12 (17%)	23 (32%)	37 (51%)	72 (36%)
	Other Professionals	3 (8%)	22 (61%)	11 (31%)	36 (18%)
	Business Person	6 (12%)	20 (42%)	22 (46%)	48 (24%)
	Housewives	11 (25%)	18 (41%)	15 (34%)	44 (22%)
Total		32 (16%)	83 (42%)	85 (42%)	200

Out of 108 executives and other professionals, 48 (44%) have positive, 45 (42%) have neutral, and the rest 15 (14%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. This finding implies that consumers who are executives and other professionals have neutral attitude toward vacuum cleaner. On the other hand, out of 48 businessmen, 22 (46%) have positive, 20 (42%) have neutral, and the rest 6 (12%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. Thus, it is found that consumers who are business persons have weakly positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner. Out of 44 housewives, 15 (34%) have positive, 18 (41%) have neutral, and the rest 11 (25%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. This implies that consumers who are housewives have very weakly positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner. In aggregate, 85 (42%) have positive, 83 (42%) have neutral, and the rest 32 (16%) have negative attitude. Therefore, it can be plausibly concluded that consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner is more or less positive in Dhaka City. However, consumers' attitudes toward vacuum cleaner slightly vary depending on their professions (see Table 18).

Table 18: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.267	6	.056
Likelihood Ratio	12.059	6	.061
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.263	1	.133
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 19 represents consumer attitude toward rice cooker by occupation. Out of 108 executives

Table 19: Attitude Toward Rice Cooker by Occupation

		Attitude Toward Rice Cooker			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Occupation	Executives	15 (21%)	35 (49%)	22 (30%)	72 (36%)
	Other Professionals	8 (22%)	15 (42%)	13 (36%)	36 (18%)
	Business Person	8 (17%)	24 (50%)	16 (33%)	48 (24%)
	Housewives	18 (42%)	18 (40%)	8 (18%)	44 (22%)
Total		49 (25%)	92 (46%)	59 (29%)	200

Table 20: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.888(a)	6	.129
Likelihood Ratio	9.514	6	.147
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.311	1	.069
N of Valid Cases	200		

and other professionals, 35 (33%) have positive, 50 (46%) have neutral, and the rest 23 (21%) have negative attitude toward rice cooker. This finding implies that consumers who are executives and other professionals have very slightly positive attitude toward rice cooker. On the other hand, out of 48 businessmen, 16 (33%) have positive, 24 (50%) have neutral, and the rest 8 (17%) have negative attitude toward rice cooker. Thus, it is found that consumers who are business persons have weakly positive attitude toward rice cooker. Out of 44 housewives, 8 (18%) have positive, 18 (40%) have neutral, and the rest 18 (42%) have negative attitude toward rice cooker. This implies that consumers who are housewives have weakly negative attitude toward rice cooker. In aggregate, 59 (29%) have positive, 92 (46%) have neutral, and the rest 49 (25%) have negative attitude. Therefore, it can be plausibly concluded that consumer attitude toward rice cooker is very weakly positive in Dhaka City. However, consumers' attitudes toward rice cooker do not vary significantly depending on their professions (see Table 20).

Table 21: Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner by Family Income

		Attitude Toward Vacuum Cleaner			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Family Income	40,000-60,000	23 (17%)	63 (47%)	47 (36%)	133 (77%)
	Above 60,000-80,000	6 (18%)	12 (35%)	16 (47%)	34 (17%)
	Above 80,000-100,000	2 (12%)	6 (35%)	9 (53%)	17 (8%)
	Above 1,00,000	1 (6%)	2 (13%)	13 (81%)	16 (8%)
Total		32 (16%)	83 (42%)	85 (42%)	200

Table 22: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.018	6	.029
Likelihood Ratio	14.392	6	.026
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.259	1	.002
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 21 shows that 167 (83.5%) have Taka 40,000 to Taka 80,000, 33 (16.5%) have above Taka 100,000 monthly income. Among the low income group, 63 (38%) have positive attitude, 75 (45%) have neutral attitude, and 29 (17%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. This implies that this group has a more or less positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner. On the other hand, among the high income group, 22 (67%) have positive attitude, 8 (24%) have neutral attitude, and 3 (9%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. This implies that consumers with high monthly income have quite positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner. In aggregate, 85 (42%) have positive, 83 (42%) have neutral, and the rest 32 (16%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. However, consumers' attitudes toward vacuum cleaner significantly vary depending on their monthly income (see Table 22).

Table 23 reports consumer attitude toward rice cooker by monthly family income. From the Table it can be seen that 167 (83.5%) have Taka 40,000 to Taka 80,000, 33 (16.5%) have above Taka 100,000 monthly income. Among the low income group, 40 (24%) have positive attitude, 80 (48%) have neutral attitude, and 47 (28%) have negative attitude

toward rice cooker. This implies that this group has a weakly negative attitude toward rice cooker. On the other hand, among the high income group, 19 (58%) have positive attitude, 12 (36%) have neutral attitude, and 2 (6%) have negative attitude toward rice cooker. This implies that consumers with high monthly income have more or less positive attitude toward vacuum cleaner. In aggregate, 59 (29%) have positive, 92 (46%) have neutral, and the rest 49 (25%) have negative attitude toward vacuum cleaner. Therefore, it can be concluded that consumers' attitudes toward rice cooker in Dhaka City is weakly positive. However, consumers' attitudes toward rice cooker significantly vary depending on their monthly income (see Table 24).

Table 23: Attitude Toward Rice Cooker by Family Income

		Attitude Toward Rice Cooker			Total
		Not a useful product	A somewhat useful product	A very useful product	
Family Income	40,000-60,000	38 (29%)	66 (50%)	29 (22%)	133 (77%)
	Above 60,000-80,000	9 (26%)	14 (41%)	11 (32%)	34 (17%)
	Above 80,000-1,00,000	1 (6%)	7 (41%)	9 (53%)	17 (8%)
	Above 1,00,000	1 (6%)	5 (31%)	10 (63%)	16 (8%)
Total		49 (25%)	92 (46%)	59 (29%)	200

Table 24: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.765	6	.005
Likelihood Ratio	19.023	6	.004
Linear-by-Linear Association	15.916	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

5. Conclusion, Generalization, and Marketing Implications

The present paper attempted to have an understanding about attitudes of consumers toward two new products—vacuum cleaner and rice cooker used for household purposes.

The results of the findings of this study suggest that in Dhaka City consumers' attitudes toward new products are weakly positive. However, consumers' attitudes toward new products vary from consumer to consumer and product to product depending on their age, gender, family income, and educational background. But occupation of consumers does not always play important role in forming their attitudes toward new products, at least in Dhaka City. It was found that consumer attitude toward vacuum cleaner is weakly positive because majority of consumers believe that traditional brooms are better than vacuum cleaners. Thus, this study finds contradictory attitudes of some respondents toward vacuum cleaners and rice cookers. This is perhaps due to the fact that in our culture, vacuum cleaners and rice cookers are not yet acceptable as a means of cleaning floors and cooking rice, respectively. However, respondents who said that rice cookers and vacuum cleaners are "somewhat useful" products are willing to purchase them, not because they are useful, but because they are symbols of social status. Some of them want to buy these two products due to demonstration effect and/or because they want to "keep up with Joneses". The findings also suggest that marketers should target both men and women consumers and inform them about the usefulness of vacuum cleaners and rice cookers and should convince them that use of these two products are hassle free and convenient. On the other hand, marketers should inform both men and women consumers about the affordable prices of vacuum cleaners and rice cookers, since some consumers believe that these two products are expensive as long as branded items are considered. Marketers should educate through promotional campaign that rice cookers and vacuum cleaners of brand names reduce customer risk associated with new products in general.

6. References

1. Booz, Allen, & Hamilton. (1982). *New Products Management for the 1980s'*, Booz, Allen & Hamilton, New York, *CF Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, Marketing Management* 12th Edition. Prentice-Hall Inc. New Jersey, USA, p. 349.
2. Cateora, Philip R. and Graham, John L. (2007). *International Marketing*, 13th Edition. McGraw-Hill Irwin, Boston, USA.
3. Hofstede, Greet and Bond, Michael Harris. (1988). The Confucius Connection, *Organizational Dynamics*, Vol. 16, No. 4, pp. 4-21.
4. Hofstede, Greet. (2001). *Culture's Consequences*, 2nd Edition. Thousand Oaks, CA, USA.
5. Hawkins, Del I., Best, Roger J., and Coney, Kenneth A. (2001). *Consumer Behavior: Building Marketing Strategy*, 8th Edition. McGraw-Hill Irwin, Boston, USA.
6. Hawkins, Del I., Mothersbaugh, David L., and Best, Roger J. (2007). *Consumer Behavior: Building Marketing Strategy*, 10th Edition. McGraw-Hill Irwin, Boston, USA.
7. Schiffman, Leon G. and Kanuk Leslie L. (2004). *Consumer behavior*, 8th Edition. Prentice-Hall Inc., New Jersey, USA.

